

2025 City Mayor Debate with Questions by the Filipino Citizens

DEBATE PARA SA BAYAN

HINDI PERA ANG MAGDIDIKTA NG KINABUKASAN NG PILIPINAS. SA DEBATE, PATAS ANG LABAN.

Suggested Format:

A debate with at least two hundred attendees.

- The list of the first 100 attendees shall come from one political party, while the second 100 attendees shall come from another political party.

No need to disclose the names of the 200 attendees. Just wear two colors representing who they support.

All attendees shall put their question on a piece of paper 15 minutes before the start of

the debate. They shall put it in a box at the table in front of the two Mayor aspirants.

The first 10 questions shall be randomly chosen one by one by the two Mayor aspirants as debate questions. After 10 questions, all the 200 guests can make a majority vote, whether to continue with another round of 10 questions.

There shall be two moderators of the debate: one from one political party, and the second from another political party.

The time limit to answer each question, and the rebuttal for each question, can follow the same format as the last Senatorial Debate organized by GMA7.

Suggested Time and Venue: City Hall at 8:00am from Monday to Friday. Facebook live so everyone can watch.

Note:

The format can be adjusted accordingly if there are three or more Mayor aspirants in a city. The same format above can be used by the Vice Mayor, Governor, Vice Governor, Congressman, Councilors, and Board Member aspirants.

This is my 27th unorthodox solution on how to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines.

Let's all end the political dynasty by allowing highly qualified Filipinos to debate fairly—no political machineries, no huge number of supporters. Just mind, character, platforms, and vision for the Filipino people.

Para sa Pilipinas !!!